

Report for the Year July 2015 – June 2016

Website of the WG: <http://www.imia-medinfo.org/new2/node/145>

LinkedIn of the WG: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3680642>

Chair (2015 - 2017)

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1. **Background** – Brief description of the WG mission, vision, and objective

IMIA's WG Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (formerly known as the Medical Concept Representation Working Group up to 2014) is an international forum for state-of-the-art dialogue and collaboration on semantics in healthcare and biomedical research, encompassing language, biomedical terminologies and ontologies. Since its formation, the working group was charged with: (1) Reviewing health data terminology and classification needs for the world community; (2) Evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs; and (3) Recommending methods for future terminology systems.

1. **Achievement** - Events and projects conducted and publications completed

At MEDINFO 2015 in São Paulo, we organized to successful events:

1. Business meeting. In this meeting, Ronald Cornet was elected as the new chair. The outgoing chair, Stefan Schulz, was elected as vice-chair together with László Balkanyi, who continues in this role. Furthermore, a brief historical overview and an outlook to the future were presented and discussed.
2. Workshop “Biomedical Semantics in the Big Data Era”. This well-attended workshop covered ontologies, natural language processing, and use of these for decision support and predictive modeling.

1. **Participation** - Engagement and participation in IMIA and health informatics events and activities

In addition to the above-mentioned activities, members have been involved in projects, such as the European project ASSESS-CT, and have submitted a proposal that was accepted for presentation at HEC2016/MIE2016 in Munich, August 2016. Besides, Stefan Schulz represented the LaMB WG as a panelist at NI 2016 in Geneva, June 2016, together with representatives of other IMIA WGs, in a panel on social media.

1. **Outreach** - Recruitment and engagement of new members and target communities, publicity and representation at major events and/or on social media

The LinkedIn group has over 100 members. In this group the WG leadership publishes regular updates on relevant events.

1. **Collaboration** - Working with other IMIA WG/SIGs or external organisations or institutions

In the workshop held at MEDINFO 2015 the chairs of various working groups of related organizations participated: EFMI NLP, AMIA KR+S, AMIA KDM, and AMIA NLP.